

CONDENSATION OF MALONIC ACID WITH ALDEHYDES. PART XXIII WITH *o*-ETHOXYBENZALDEHYDE

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o-Ethoxybenzaldehyde has been condensed with malonic acid. In the presence of a trace of pyridine, it gave nearly a quantitative yield of *o*-ethoxycinnamic acid, m. p. 133-34°; in the absence of any condensing agent, it gave a small amount (8%) of the same acid with 68% of the *o*-ethoxybenzylidene-malonic acid.

o-Ethoxybenzaldehyde has been condensed by Perkin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1881, 39, 413) with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride in a sealed tube at 160-180°, as a result of which he obtained what he called β -ethyl-*o*-oxyphenylacrylic acid (m. p. 135°). The yield is not given, but it could not possibly be as good as is obtained in the present experiment. Here the *o*-ethoxybenzaldehyde, malonic acid and pyridine (in 1:1:0.16 mol.) were heated on a water-bath: one experiment in which the heating was done for 6 hours gave almost a quantitative yield of the same *o*-ethoxycinnamic acid. As is usual in these condensations, in the presence of pyridine, salicylaldehyde is the only aldehyde to give coumarin (Kurien and Pandya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 824; Khan, Kurien and Pandya, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1935, 1, 440) i. e. the *cis*-form; in all the others, as in *o*-methoxybenzaldehyde (Pandya and Vahidy, *ibid.*, 1937, 5A, 437) and in *o*-ethoxybenzaldehyde, the *trans*-form is the only form obtained.

An attempt was also made to obtain the undecarboxylated *o*-ethoxybenzylidene-malonic acid. This was obtained (m. p. 174-75°) when the aldehyde and malonic acid were heated alone on a water-bath for 4 hours, when about 8% yield of the *o*-ethoxycinnamic acid and 68% yield of the dibasic acid were obtained.

Stuart's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1888, 53, 142) of heating the two with glacial acetic acid was also tried; the condensation did not appear to have taken place at all on the water-bath, even on 20 hours' heating. The temperature was gradually raised to 140°-150°, when a product came out, but at that temperature and with a long heating time it was only the monobasic *o*-ethoxycinnamic acid in about 60% yield. Comparison of the yields from salicylaldehyde and its methyl and ethyl ethers shows very clearly that while the hydroxy group in the *ortho* position has given the lowest yield, the methoxy and the ethoxy groups in the same position have given almost the theoretical yields in the presence of a trace of pyridine; when no condensing agent is used, the ethoxy derivative gives the best yield.

EXPERIMENTAL

In the presence of a trace of Pyridine.—*o*-Ethoxybenzaldehyde (1.5 g.), malonic acid (1.0 g.) and pyridine (0.13 g.) (prepared as usual, and in 1:1:0.16 mol. proportion) were heated together on a water-bath for 4 hours. The reaction was very quick, as liquefaction and formation of a white solid took place in 1 hour. After cooling over-

night, the product was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution, and it gave on acidification a white substance. It was washed well with water, and on drying it melted at 130°; yield 1.3 g. on recrystallisation (alcohol), the final melting-point was 133-34°. Perkin gives m. p. 135° (*loc. cit.*). Titration against caustic soda solution gave equivalent, 191.5; *o*-ethoxycinnamic acid, C₁₁H₁₂O₃, requires equiv., 192. The yield was 67.7%.

In a second experiment the heating was for 6 hours, when the yield was 1.9 g. (99%).

In the absence of any Condensing Agent.—The acid and the aldehyde were heated alone (1:1 mol.) on a water-bath for 4 hours. A yellow product was obtained, which was treated with sodium bicarbonate solution and dilute hydrochloric acid; a white precipitate was then obtained and from the filtrate, a yellow substance was obtained by extraction with ether.

The white substance, crystallised from alcohol, melted at 133-34°, and a mixed melting point with the product of the previous experiment showed that it was the *o*-ethoxycinnamic acid (titration with NaOH solution gave equiv., 191.6). The yield was only 0.16 g. (8.3% of theory).

The crude yellow product melted at 167°, and after recrystallisation (alcohol) yellow needles were obtained, m. p. 174-75° (with effervescence). When heated at 175° for 15 minutes till the effervescence had stopped, and then cooled, it changed into a solid melting at 127-28°, which is near to that of the mono-acid.

The yellow acid is the corresponding malonic acid. [Found: equivalent (by titration), 120.0; (by silver salt), 120.1; M. W. (Rast), 233.5. *o*-Ethoxybenzmalonic acid, C₁₂H₁₄O₅, requires equiv., 118.0; M. W., 236]. The yield was 1.6 g. (68% of theory). The total yield of the two acids was thus over 76%.

TABLE I

Aldehyde	Heated at for	Catalyst.	Product.	Yield	Ref.
Salicylaldehyde	100°. 18 hrs.	Pyridide trace	Coumarin-carboxylic acid	57%	Kurien & Pandya, (<i>J. I. C. S.</i> , 1944, 11, 823)
<i>o</i> -Ethoxybenzaldehyde	" 5	"	<i>o</i> -Methoxy-cinnamic acid	Nearly 100%	Pandya & Vahidy, <i>Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.</i> , 1937, 8, 439
<i>o</i> -Ethoxybenzaldehyde	" 6	"	<i>o</i> -Ethoxy-cinnamic acid	"	(Present paper)
Salicylaldehyde	" 5	None	<i>o</i> -Coumarin-carboxylic acid	11%	Khan, Kurien, Pandya, <i>Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.</i> , 1935, 1, 441
<i>o</i> -Methoxybenzaldehyde	" "	"	<i>o</i> -Methoxy-cinnamic acid	48%	Pandya & Vahidy (<i>loc. cit.</i>)
<i>o</i> -Ethoxybenzaldehyde	" 5	"	Mixture <i>o</i> -ethoxy-cinnamic acid & <i>o</i> -ethoxy benzylidene-malonic acid	8% 68%	Present Paper

In the presence of Glacial Acetic Acid.—The same quantities of the aldehyde and the acid were heated with 6 g. of glacial acetic acid (1:1: 3.6 mol.) on a water-bath for 20 hours; no condensation could be detected to have taken place in a test sample taken out. The temperature was then raised to 110° and maintained for 7 hours, yet no product could be detected. Four hours' heating at 125-130° also proved ineffective. Only when the oil-bath was raised to 140-150° and maintained for 4 hours, a solid began to separate out. The whole mixture was then poured into a large quantity of water, the insoluble portion dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution, and reprecipitated by means of dilute acid; after filtering, washing and drying it was found to melt at 131°; on recrystallisation the melting point rose to 133-34° and it was identified as the *o*-ethoxycinnamic acid. The yield was 1.1 g. (about 60%). No dibasic acid was isolated: it must have been first formed, but was not isolable.

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